

TRACTION SEPARATION RESPONSE OF A UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITE IN INTRALAMINAR MODE I FRACTURE; EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

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ABSTRACT

Fracture of carbon fiber reinforced composites (CFRPs) is dominated by large scale fiber bridging which acts as a very important toughening mechanism. The objective of this work is to investigate the intralaminar Mode I fracture & its mechanisms in a unidirectional CFRP composite. For this purpose double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens of height $H=6$ & 10 mm with a symmetric, diamond wire sawed, intralaminar precrack, have been produced by cutting a composite plate.

For the realistic evaluation of the bridging effect on crack growth resistance, optical fibers with 10 multiplexed Bragg grating (FBG) sensors have been glued on the exterior upper surface of selected specimens, to capture the strain profile during the fracture experiment. Numerical FE simulations of the DCB experiment are carried out with a variable bridging tractions' profile. The profile is expressed as a function of the maximum bridging traction, the bridging zone length & an exponential softening parameter. The simulated strain profile is compared with the experimental strains & an iterative procedure minimizes their difference. The optimized strain distribution corresponds to a bridging traction's profile, with a maximum bridging traction of ~ 8.3 MPa. The resulted resistance-curves illustrate a maximum energy release rate (ERR) of 20% higher for the thick specimen. Moreover, the plateau ERR is ~ 2.3 times higher than the corresponding interlaminar one, although having the same initial fracture toughness.

The calculated energy contribution of bridging agrees very well with the produced resistance-curves. The resulted bridging law is applied over a cohesive element model to reproduce the load-displacement curves.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials and in particular carbon/epoxy fiber systems are dominating more and more industrial sectors leading to an intense need in characterization of their fracture response. Fracture of these materials initiates and propagates within resin epoxy paths, since the matrix is by far the weakest component. Nevertheless, fracture of fiber reinforced composites is dominated by fiber bridging, which acts as a very important toughening mechanism. Important results have been reported on the delamination mechanisms of unidirectional laminates [1, 2, 4-7] using different approaches. However, investigations into intralaminar fracture have not yet received the same level of attention owing to the lack of standards in introducing the crack & the density of the large scale, fiber bridging during crack propagation [3, 8]. Still, the intralaminar fracture propagation is a more realistic scenario of a structural component since it may initiate by machining defects.

The conventional approach in the characterization of the resistance to fracture of a composite material is based on the energy release rate (ERR) calculations, which can be represented in a resistance curve (R-curve). On a typical R-curve the initial fracture energy is defined at the onset of

the crack initiation and the maximum ERR at the steady fracture state (or a specimen's global fracture) as the sum of the initiation energy plus the maximum energetic contribution of the bridging tractions. When large-scale bridging occurs, the R-curve is not a sufficient tool to describe the fracture response of a structure. Therefore, the bridging tractions profile versus the crack opening displacements (CODs), as conventionally called, the bridging law, should be defined. The bridging law has been initially considered as one unique relation, independent of specimen geometry [1-3]. On the other hand, later research studies [6, 7] describe the existence of a specimen thickness effect (rigidity effect) on the maximum ERR.

To characterize the bridging tractions profile the following methods have been used in the literature: a) direct methods [1-3], which rely on the application of Rice's approach [16], for the calculation of ERR, and b) indirect methods [4-7], which employ the strain field, due to delamination, and compare it with a numerical model and identify bridging parameters.

This work is dealing with the systematic characterization of Mode I failure of unidirectional composites in an intralaminar plane. For the experimental procedure a simple double cantilever beam (DCB) configuration is used. The bridging traction profile is calculated by an inverse iterative procedure, comparing the experimental strain data, acquired from multiplexed FBGs from an optical fiber, with numerical data from a model including the objective bridging traction profile. This robust analysis aims at a complete fracture characterization of intralaminar Mode I fracture, defining the exact bridging traction's field while pinpointing the effects of rigidity on ERR and the resulted bridging law.

2 METHODS

2.1 Materials-specimens

Double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens have been produced from a composite plate, fabricated by manual-lay-up of 50 unidirectional layers of the carbon/epoxy prepreg system SE-70 from Gurit SPTM, using standard autoclave procedures in vacuum conditions and 3bar of uniform pressure. The cured plate has a thickness of 10mm, which represents the width of the DCB specimens, a length of 360mm and a width of 200mm. One single plate is used to cut the beam specimens of height $H = 6$ & 10mm and length 340mm; a uniform frame of 10mm width is wasted from the plates to eliminate the effects of the manual lay-up procedure.

Subsequently, a 60mm intralaminar precrack has been introduced in each beam by the use of diamond wire saw, with a wire diameter of $\varnothing 130\mu\text{m}$, to create symmetric DCB specimens. One side of the specimens is accurately marked by means of a ruler with a step of **1mm**, to easily monitor the crack propagation. For the application of the wedge forces, cubic loading blocks of 10mm side and pin holes of 4mm, are glued on each specimen by use of an Araldite[®] 5min epoxy adhesive.

The material properties of the cured plate have been calculated using both experimental data and the rule of mixtures formulation [13]. For the acquisition of the E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{13} moduli ($-11-$ is the direction of the fibers), the corresponding ASTM standard experimental procedures [9-11] have been processed. Based on these data and values provided by the manufacturer, a volume fraction of 54% has been calculated. Additional properties for an orthotropic laminate case have been calculated using the rule of mixtures for fiber properties as obtained by Kriz et al [12] and the resin properties provided by Gurit SPTM. The resulted material properties are represented in Table 1.

For the accurate inverse-iterative estimation of the bridging effect on the crack growth resistance, optical fibers with 10 multiplexed Bragg gratings (FBG) sensors are glued on the exterior surface of two selected specimens (one of each thickness), to capture the exact strain profile during the fracture experiment. Each optical fiber has been carefully cleaned from the plastic coating, applying sulfuric acid, before being bonded by means of a liquid cyanoacrylate instant adhesive (Loctite[®] 401), positioned on the center of specimen's exterior surface.

Engineering constant		Experimental	Calculated
E_{11}	[GPa]	118.7	
E_{22}, E_{33}	[GPa]	7.7	
G_{12}, G_{13}	[GPa]	3.8	
G_{23}	[GPa]		3.1
ν_{12}, ν_{13}	–		0.314
ν_{23}	–		0.427

Table 1: Laminate Engineering Constants.

2.2 Experimental procedure

The experimental procedure used in this work conforms to the ASTM standards [17] for the interlaminar fracture characterization. A simple (DCB) Mode I test rig is used, with the load applied to the specimen by loading blocks. The experiment is conducted in displacement control, with a constant rate of 3mm/min.

Crack propagation is monitored by means of a high resolution CCD camera which constantly records the crack tip location. Due to the linearity of load-displacement curves, the Mode I intralaminar fracture energy, described by the ERR (G) for each crack length, is calculated by the use of the Compliance Calibration Method [15] for a linear elastic case, defined by the following formula:

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \quad (1)$$

where P , is the applied load, B is specimen's width, C is the compliance and a is the crack length. Note that (1) is the result of $G = -dII/B \cdot da$, when the load-displacement curves are linear. The application of the compliance calibration method requires the usage of the experimentally acquired values for the compliance and the crack length in a fitting scheme to create the compliance versus crack length function $C(a)$. The simple power law Compliance Calibration (CC) method [17], provides a satisfactory fitting, however, it fails to follow the rapid decrease of specimen compliance due to very large scale bridging in intralaminar fracture. The Modified Compliance Calibration (MCC) [17], [18] can provide more accurate fitting being able to capture the gradient of compliance and this method is used for the production of the R-curves. Nevertheless, for such a large scale bridging one should reinvestigate the accuracy of the calibration methods which were built on a basis of small changes in compliance or better in ERR throughout an experiment. For this reason a segmented CC method has been used on the evaluation of the two critical regions on an R-Curve. The first segment consists of the steep transitional part of the R-curve and the second of the data from the plateau state regions.

2.3 Strain acquisition and processing

The strains are acquired from 10 multiplexed FBGs with a reflected Bragg wavelength, λ_{B0} , with a range between 1520 and 1565nm, and a spacing distance of 4mm resulting to a strain measurement region of ~40mm. The exact position of the Bragg grating on the specimen, after the gluing procedure, has been identified by the use of the Optical Low Coherence Reflectometry OLCR technique [14], with a scanning spatial resolution of 50 μ m.

The strains are captured by the use of a Micron Optics SM130 system. The strain acquisition technique [14] is based on the FBG property to reflect a characteristic Bragg wavelength of the broadband source light that is introduced in the objective optical fiber (Fig. 1). As the optical fiber is exposed on a uniform strain field, the Bragg grating wavelength is shifted proportionally to strains' magnitude. In such a case, where the temperature field is steady and the dominant strain is the axial, while the rest components may be negligible, the relationship between the wavelength shift and the axial strain is given by (2):

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = (1 - p_e)\varepsilon_z \quad (2)$$

where $p_e=0.2148$ is the optomechanical coefficient that can be obtained experimentally.

Figure 1: Bragg grating principal and specimen with glued optical fiber.

The compressive strain's profile for the thin specimen ($H=6\text{mm}$) are depicted in Fig. 2. In order to obtain a continuous strain distribution for a particular moment on crack's propagation, within the steady fracture state, the strain versus time data are initially converted to strain versus crack length. Afterwards, they are shifted towards a unique origin based on the relative position of the FBGs. These data are used in the objective strain profile of the inverse characterization method at a specific crack length.

Figure 2: (a) Strains versus time, per FBG, (b) Strains versus distance from crack tip, per FBG.

2.4 Numerical approach-reverse identification

The inverse identification technique is built over the optimization of the strain's profile produced by a 2D, FE, plain strain model of the DCB experiment with the objective bridging tractions' profile as the parametric input applied over the potential bridging zone. The numerical strains have been optimized while compared with the ones acquired from the FBG gages during testing [4-7]. The experimental strains have been enriched assuming a self-similar stress state for $\pm 2\text{mm}$ of crack

propagation within the steady state of fracture. Using this method the optimization becomes more reliable having more reference points.

The parameters that define the bridging tractions $\sigma_{br}(z)$ (Fig. 3(a)) form an exponential softening function depending on the bridging zone length, z_{max} , the maximum traction at the crack tip, σ_{max} and an exponential decrease coefficient, γ . These three parameters are identified by iteratively comparing the experimental strain data with the numerical ones. The optimization scheme is enriched by one more offset parameter χ , with a range of ~ 2 mm, defining the uncertainty of crack tip's position originating from the transition of strain vs. time to crack length data. Coupling this feature with the absence of a direct effect of crack tip's singular strain field (since the optical fiber is placed on the exterior surface of the specimen), the optimization algorithm minimizes the norm of the residual error of the experimental strains versus the numerical ones, plus the error of the numerically calculated J integral [16] at the crack tip, compared with the initial toughness G_{in} . The J_{tip} is calculated using Abaqus v6.12 contour integral tool, which is using the virtual crack extension formulation in absence of body forces, thermal strains and crack face tractions as described by Anderson [15]. In all models, the elements at the vicinity of the crack are modified to capture the singularity of $1/\sqrt{r}$ (r indicates the distance from the crack tip).

The error minimization scheme utilizes the 'lsqnonlin' optimization routine of Matlab 8.0. The optimized error function is depicted in the following equation (3):

$$erf(\sigma_{max}, z_{max}, \gamma, \chi, J_{tip}) = \frac{1}{2} \left\| \frac{\epsilon_{FEM} - \epsilon_{exp}}{\epsilon_{exp}}, \left[\frac{J_{tip} - G_{in}}{G_{in}} \right]_{rank(\epsilon_{exp})} \right\| \quad (3)$$

The numerical model is schematically shown in Fig. 3(a), and in Fig. 3(b) are illustrated the objective experimental strain data and the resulted optimized numerical strains for both the two investigated thicknesses.

Figure 3: (a) Schematic of numerical model and input, (b) Experimental strains and the optimized numerical strain profile.

The identified results for the bridging tractions profile have been verified by use of a cohesive numerical FE model in Abaqus v6.12, where the bridging traction properties are employed over a zero thickness cohesive element layer. The cohesive law implemented at the cohesive elements can be divided into two parts: 1. a triangular, linear softening part to employ the initiation fracture toughness G_{in} , representing the initial failure of the matrix and 2. an exponential softening part, representing the traction separation relation of bridging traction $\hat{\sigma}_{br}(\delta)$, versus the CODs, with an energetic contribution equal to G_{br} . The damage parameter of the cohesive elements for the initial softening part has been calculated as described by Camanho et al [19]. The cohesive response is completed by the calculated bridging tractions as a function of the CODs. The overall behavior, after damage, is summarized in the following equation (4):

$$\sigma = (1 - D)K_0\delta \text{ with}$$

$$D = \frac{\delta_1(\delta - \delta_c)}{\delta(\delta_1 - \delta_c)}, \text{ for } \delta_c < \delta \leq \delta_1 \text{ and } D = 1 - \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{br}}{K_0\delta}, \text{ for } \delta_1 < \delta \leq \delta_f \quad (4)$$

and is schematically represented in Fig. 5(a).

The damage initiation point is taken equal to the 90° tensile strength of the material as given by Gurit SP™ and is equal to 42MPa. The ratio between δ_0/δ_1 is chosen equal to 1%, serving convergency purposes of the numerical solution enabling the management of the elastic recovery after element's failure. This scheme provides an initial stiffness for the cohesive elements of $\sim 327\text{GPa}$ being about 40 times greater than the E_{22} modulus of the material. Therefore, it has been assured that the compliance of the cohesive layer has a negligible effect on the overall response of the model.

3 RESULTS

3.1 R-curves

The resulted R-curves are represented in Fig. 4(a). These curves are created using the MCC method and they are the averages of at least 5 specimens per thickness. The error bars represent the standard deviation of the total number of experiments. This intralaminar system intrinsically shows a tendency for fluctuations in the R-curves. This behavior originates from the lack of a well-defined rich resin path, compared with an interlaminar fracture scenario. This effect can also be visible on the size of the bridging bundles Fig. 4(b) which can reach a diameter of 0.5mm.

Comparing these ERR results with the corresponding interlaminar values it can be extracted that the fracture energy is about 2.2-2.3 times higher than the interlaminar results for the exact same material, on similar beam thicknesses [7]. However, the ERR for crack initiation is the same around 285J/m^2 by the CC and $\sim 260\text{J/m}^2$ with the MCC approach.

Furthermore, the resulted R-curves (Fig. 4(a)) illustrate a higher ERR at the steady state of about 20% for the thicker beam-specimen proving a strong thickness effect in maximum fracture toughness.

Figure 4: (a) Averaged R-curves per thickness, (b) Snapshot of fractured specimens for H=6mm.

3.2 Traction separation relations

The semi-experimental analysis performed in this work, provides the tractions separation relations which are illustrated in Fig. 5(a). Interestingly, a unique thickness-independent maximum bridging traction of $\sim 8.3\text{MPa}$ has been identified. The maximum bridging zone length is calculated equal to 25.5mm for the thin specimen and 40.5mm for the thick specimen. The exponential softening parameter γ ranged from 0.082 for H=10mm, to 0.12 for H=6mm.

3.3 Cohesive models

The cohesive models are built using quadratic plain strain elements (Abaqus CPE8R) for the beams and linear cohesive elements (Abaqus COH2D4) for the cohesive layer. The length ratio between these elements is 1/25, quite bigger than the minimum recommended [20] for such model cases, so that the static FE solver converges managing very small crack increments. The load-displacement curves are illustrated in Fig. 5(b). In this figure the experimental data are compared with the calculated curves from the cohesive models and they present a quite good concurrence.

Figure 5: (a) Traction separation relation and numerically implemented cohesive law, (b) load-displacement responses, experimental & numerical.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- The intralaminar fracture phenomenon describes a strong damage-tolerant mechanism, with the ERRs at the steady state to be toughening of about 9 times compared with the initiation values due to the large scale bridging.
- The maximum ERR is much higher than the corresponding interlaminar values [7] as it has also been reported in previous works [8].
- The maximum bridging traction is thickness independent and equal to 8.3MPa. This value is ~ 5 times smaller than the material's transverse strength. The corresponding maximum traction reported in previous works [3] is significantly smaller for similar R-curves.
- The bridging zone length is smaller compared with the delamination mechanism and this can also be depicted in the initial steep part of the R-curves (Fig. 4) before the plateau state.
- The investigated rigidity effect on the R-curves is of quite high importance illustrating an ERR of 1.2 times higher for the thick beam-specimens. These results, together with previous works [6], [7] draw a different framework on the treatment of R-curves in damage tolerant design with large scale bridging phenomena suggesting the importance of the stiffness effects in fracture mechanism.
- The implemented iterative, semi-experimental method provides very reliable results. This is evident since the cohesive element model, with the determined traction separation relation, predicts very well the load-displacement curves and moreover, the calculated energetic contribution of bridging coincides with the R-curves.

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